

The user-researcher perspective

Initial findings for roundtable discussion

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Top force: intention

The desire

Strong desire to carry out research that is equitable, inclusive and diverse.

Second force: the broader situation

Time pressure

- * deadlines

Financial pressure

- * lack of resource

Organisational flux

- * staff change position / role
- * staff / agency staff on short term contracts
- * staff and project turnover
- * changes in organisational structure, leadership, direction and role

Third force: doing research

Rigid and standardised procedure

- * difficult and time consuming to adapt
- * expectation to use templates / procedures which may not be accessible for everyone
- * extra safeguarding procedures for 'vulnerable' participants
- * expected to create usability tasks before recruiting participants

Tackling organisational culture

- * ingrained ideas about diversity and inclusion
- * helping clients understand good EDI practice

Working within organisational structure

- * no authority to push ideas
- * deadlines / delivery decided elsewhere
- * usability testing is an afterthought / at the end of the project

Working within a defined project

- * tight deadline
- * budget
- * scope decided by clients and stakeholders
- * need to commit to approaches early – like ethical approval before recruitment

Getting guidance

- * siloed teams – knowledge is spread not centralised
- * lack of / unable to access guidance
- * lack of feedback / dialogue between researchers and stakeholders
- * creating usability tasks which are representative of diverse usage

Needing research credibility

- * expectation of a single, predefined experiment with consistent procedures
- * expectation of controlling for differences

Recruiting participants

- * existing channels (databases) lacking diversity
- * working with voluntary / faith groups but not able to develop long-term relationships
- * project deadline pressures
- * recruiting people who can fit available slots (see *research space*)

Getting access to research space

- * lack of accessible, physical space
- * limited availability of physical space
- * needing the right equipment to support participants with usability tasks
- * organisational restriction on communication technology options

Researcher worries

- * ethical approaches, including compensation
- * not knowing people's needs
- * safeguarding participants and the research team

Fourth force: the reality

Working within restraints

It is difficult to take a flexible approach. Do the best I can within the constraints in which I am operating.